

Blockchain in energy : a new paradigm for Local Energy Communities (LEC) of the 4IR

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Abstract

The development of renewable energy sources into the energy sector introduced a rapid shift from traditional centralized energy systems to distributed energy systems. DES are more open to competitive auction-based energy supply with constant interaction between the main power utilities and participants of independent power producing plants. However, these energy systems requires increased reliance on advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and so forth which is on the cusp of innovations in blockchain development. Blockchain technology provides improved visibility, transparency, better organization as well as data exchange across boundaries, which result in more acute decision making and increased system operating efficiency. This article provide an overview on how blockchain would work in relation to energy and how we can use it to optimize transaction procedures among energy participants within the fast growing and distributed energy sector and the emergent Local Energy Communities (LEC).

Keywords

Distributed Energy System (DES), Energy Market, Independent Power Producer (IPP), Demand Side Response (DSR), peer-to-peer (P2P), Dispensed Ledger Generation (DLT), Local Energy Community (LEC)

1. Introduction

Electricity systems are being challenged by the introduction of high volumes of renewable energy generation from decentralized sources that demand for new tools to maintain safe operation and stability. Also, the electricity sector is on the edge of digitalization with the deployment of sensors and smart devices at the premises of every consumer in numerous countries. Blockchain is discussed as 1 of the solutions and as a revolutionary technology and is right now at the top of many companies' agendas. Blockchain is a technology that spreads the power across the system, giving each person the opportunity for equal influence. No single entity controls the information in the system [1]. Furthermore, the information is open to be read by all people in the network, facilitating a transparency that has not been possible before blockchain technology.

Blockchain originates from Bitcoin, a cryptocurrency presented in 2008, and has been developed for several different use cases since then [1]. To find the right use case for

blockchain is not as simple as one might think. There are several criteria that can be used to evaluate blockchain use cases. The purpose of Bitcoin was to have a currency without central governance, as a bank. In turn, this forces transactions to take time to be secure [1]. The time for transactions and amount of transactions that can be made, affects how the blockchain can scale [2]. When designing a blockchain there is a choice between three attributes, of which only two can be achieved at once. This problem is called the trilemma and includes decentralisation, security and scalability. Therefore, solutions for scaling blockchain needs to be investigated in order to implement blockchain for other applications than cryptocurrency

One sector considering the value of using blockchain is the energy sector. The rapid expansion of digitalisation in the energy sector opens up for flexibility and will accelerate the transition into a smarter energy system [3]. In order for the energy sector to become more digital and to embrace new smart technology, as blockchain, the energy market must adjust and become more flexible.

2. Blockchain Technology

Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology where every full node in the network downloads a copy of the same ledger. The ledger is a collection of all transactions ever made on the blockchain. The original thought of blockchain was to have all transactions on the blockchain viewable to all nodes in the network. All nodes in the network need to verify a transaction for it to be completed. No third party verifies transactions, meaning that the power is distributed through the network. The transactions are stored in series in a chronological order of blocks, as soon as the transaction is verified. The blocks are then put together creating a chain of blocks, also known as a blockchain. Once a block is added to the chain it cannot be changed, making the blockchain irreversible [4].

Figure 1 illustrates an example of a blockchain. The main chain (dark blue) consists of the longest series of blocks from the genesis block to the current block. Orphan blocks (light blue) exist outside the main chain and can be from a fork. [2].

Figure 1: Block chain example [2]

2.1. Types of Blockchain Technologies

There are mainly two types of blockchains, the 1st is a public blockchain and the 2nd is a private blockchain. A public blockchain means that anyone that downloads the blockchain is able to; view transactions, verify transactions and make transactions. The first blockchain created and used for Bitcoin is called a public blockchain. When viewing transaction, the addresses of the ones making transactions are anonymous. The information showing is amount transacted and time of transaction. In contrast to public blockchains, there are also private blockchains. In private blockchains, nodes have to be accepted into the network and not every node can view, make and verify transactions. These networks are sometimes called consortiums [5].

Concept	Public Blockchain	Private Blockchain
Registration	Anonymous and free access	Invitation only Know Your Customer (KYC) control
Blockchain	Decentralised data storage and verification performed by P2P networks	Centralised/descentralised data with one or more operators
Manipulation	No ex post revisions are possible	Ex post revisions are possible
Costs	Higher operating costs	Lower operating costs with operator fees
Scope	Resilient with but low scalability	Participation controlled but very high scalability

Figure 2: Difference between public and private blockchain [6]

2.2. Blockchain in the energy sector

The energy sector is facing several challenges associated with integrating distributed renewable energy sources in the existing centralized energy system. Digital opportunities such as Internet of Things (IOT) and Blockchain are acting as enablers for the creation of a decentralized energy system. Blockchain is being tested for several applications in the energy sector as a means of resolving security and transparency linked issues as well as for improving the efficiency through the provision of a decentralized authority concept, thus creating a win-win situation for all the stakeholders. Figure 2 shows blockchain energy applications in private and public domains. In energy trading applications either at the wholesale [5] or local level, such as peer-to-peer energy trading, will provide a reliable verification process for trading without needing authentication from a third party. Having a standardized global blockchain infrastructure can also provide frictionless cross border energy trading. This will act as an enabler for prosumers to participate in the local energy market where they can rely on technology which has the potential to make the transactions faster, simpler, and cheaper than a traditional centralized energy systems. Blockchain is also being tested in electric vehicle (EV) charging facilities where it will enable access to all charging points for EV drivers by creating a network of EVs and charging facilities. The idea is to create an easy payment system that is also efficient. This in turn will advance the

platforms for energy generation and storage and the emergence of Local Energy Communities (LEC's).

Figure 3: Blockchain energy applications [6]

For blockchain to succeed in the energy sector the scalability problem must be solved. and the market needs to be properly analysed. For example, who will pay who, when and how, and how often must transactions be made? For one city, a network could be built and tested repeatedly, but to test on a larger scale might be challenging. The energy industry has a lot of potential to become more decentralised as smart grids, small scale energy production and LEC's are being developed. Today's systems based on the old billing and even smart meter systems cannot handle these changes and blockchain based systems could be the only way of making it possible. An interesting use of the technology is to create a more flexible grid is by selling your excess electricity produced by e.g. solar panels to your neighbour to charge their electric vehicle. The other way around would be selling electricity from electric vehicles to neighbours having a shortfall of production.

2.3. Off Chain Transactions

A possible long term scalability solution is the use of state channels, also called off-chain networks or payment channels. This is a channel between two actors that conduct transactions between each other. At any time suggested any of the actors can connect to the blockchain to verify the transactions made. Each actor would put cryptocurrency into a smart contract and then send transactions through the state channel [3]. This would decrease the cost per transaction, compared to making all transaction on the blockchain. For every state channel an amount of cryptocurrency set aside for every new channel. This cryptocurrency is locked in the channel until the channel is closed [3].

2.4. Local Energy Communities

The goal is to create Local Energy Communities (LEC) that can trade their own generated or stored energy with each other as described in 2.2 above. These LEC's can also decide where they want to buy their energy from, this can be directly from electricity generators without the electricity supplier but this can also be from privately owned wind farms. Prosumers will be able to join a LEC, this LEC can be the neighbourhood, a business district or a family that live all over the country. Prosumers will be able to join whatever LEC they want. Where the LEC buys electricity it up to the LEC, if the members of a LEC want to buy cheap coal energy they can do so. The prosumers of a LEC will be able to sell their own generated electricity inside the LEC too. Eventually consumers are only getting raw energy prices for their generated electricity. Trading from peer to peer inside a LEC will result in a higher reward for selling self generated energy from rooftop solar or a small solar farm, or industrial Distributed Energy System. Consumers that actively participate in the energy ecosystem by storing energy and/or generating electricity with solar panels or a wind turbine or actively joining a LEC will be named prosumers. consumers that are not part of a LEC will still be called consumers and they will get their energy through a traditional energy supplier. Blockchain would provide a transparent system to buy and sell energy from and to whomever without the need of a middleman (electricity supplier).

3. Conclusion

When relating to blockchain as an innovation in the Energy Sector, it is important to remember that the expectations around blockchain are high at the moment and this affects how blockchain is discussed. Also it should be considered that blockchain is in its incubation phase, and blockchain solutions developed today will undergo some metamorphosis in the future.

The energy sector is a landscape of many actors, and blockchain can be a tool for creating a market for both new innovations and old ones taking new shapes in the Smart Cities of the 4IR. Real value can be gained when working together across industry and company borders. This paper recognises potential in using blockchain in the energy sector for high frequency trading and the emergence of Local Energy Communities.

To conclude, the Local Energy Community using Blockchain for Energy, has two major benefits for its prosumers.

1. Lower energy costs, the LEC will buy energy directly from independent generators, Eskom, Municipality, or other LEC's. This means that where LEC's produce excess renewable energy in the community, there is no energy supplier to take a cut of the money. Resulting in lower prices per kWh for those average costs..
2. Prosumers are able to actively participate in the energy market. They can use their storage for balancing purposes in the LEC and they can sell their energy for a higher price than selling it back to an energy supplier.

4. References

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